

The Pursuit of Beauty: Motivations and Reasons Behind Why Chinese Teenage Girls Use

Makeup

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Genders, Sexualities, and Race: An Intersectional Perspective

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Abstract

Current studies on the reasons why women use makeup have been focused on and limited to samples of women from Western society of an older age. Limited research has been done on women of Eastern descent, especially Chinese women, who are between the ages of 15 and 30. This study intends to investigate and explore the common reasons and motivations behind the use of makeup by Chinese teenage girls. By interviewing eleven Chinese girls between the ages of 15 and 19, this research has found six common themes: gaining confidence, concealing facial imperfections, being presentable in pictures, looking energetic, reducing stress and pressure, and easing the transition to becoming an adult woman. These themes provide insight into the present Chinese society, the values that it imposes on young women, and the role that makeup plays in their lives.

Literature Review

Makeup is defined as “colored substances used on one’s face to improve or change one’s appearance” (Cambridge Dictionary, 2024b). Makeup has played an important role in the lives of humans since ancient times. In the past, it was often a method of communicating one’s identity. People have used makeup to demonstrate their maturity, sexuality, class, and power (Danesi, 2018). Records also show that all humans, regardless of gender, have attempted to make their bodies more beautiful through different means including makeup (Kuipers, 2022). Although cultural differences between makeup styles and makeup products exist and makeup might not be used for the same purposes as it did in the past, makeup continues to influence many peoples’ daily lives. Apart from using makeup to represent identity, makeup has increasingly become a tool for people to “look good.” This is due to the rise of a consumer culture that associates the aesthetics of people with power, an ever-growing service economy that emphasizes the

importance of looks in the work field and associates professionalism with appearance, and the privilege of the upper class's ability to manipulate their looks (Kuipers, 2022). Indeed, it is theorized that the upper class sets standards for the people of the lower class, and the lower class feels compelled to follow those challenging standards (Kuipers, 2022). China's cosmetics industry is now one of the world's largest, and it is estimated that many makeup influencers can generate more revenue than celebrities do (Ou, 2015).

Beauty Standards in China

In the late 20th century, China adopted a new ideology, transitioning from the Maoist era to the economic reform era led by Deng. Beyond visible changes in the economy, beauty standards also shifted and adapted to the Western idea of individualism. Mao had terminated the use of cosmetics as a response to his communist beliefs. On the other hand, the economic reform convinced people that beauty only belonged to those of a high social class, which most desired to become (Lotti, 2018). The new standard of physical appearance in China has also become somewhat similar to those of Western standards, as seen in the 1980s (Yan, 2022). A slim figure and a European-looking face with a tall nose and fair skin define beauty.

Although outer beauty has begun to be more valued in Chinese society, inner beauty was still arguably more important for Chinese women. Inner beauty is a concept related to Confucianist beliefs, which Chinese women believe is an important aspect of female empowerment and a belief that could help them refrain from society's beauty standards. However, the attempt to reject these beauty standards is challenging in that those standards of inner beauty is affected and constructed by certain aspects of society, such as the beauty industry that associates a good-looking face with kindness (Ma, 2023).

Contemporary Reasons for Using Makeup

Contemporary studies have found that one potential reason why women use makeup is for female self-empowerment and to express feminist beliefs. However, there is an argument between third-wave feminists who assert that makeup can be used to empower women and second-wave feminists who argue that makeup ultimately follows beauty norms and does not empower women. Hartley (2019) argued that the use of cosmetics cannot be simply defined as “in favor of” or “against” feminist ideas. The use of makeup depends strongly on the intentions of the makeup applier and the location where one is wearing makeup. On the other hand, Dimulescu (2015) argued that in the history of the objectification of the female body and the consumerist construction of beauty norms, it is challenging to determine the real reasons why women are applying makeup even though they might claim that they are doing it for empowerment. Women are unconsciously pressured to fit into the female identity that society has created. The limitation of the reason for using makeup as a feminist tool is that young Chinese girls, especially those in middle school, are unaware of the concept of feminism and most likely do not use makeup for this purpose.

Another motivation found in studies for why women use makeup is to gain erotic capital and opportunities. Dippner (2018) argued that the current economic environment in China promotes the idea that it is possible to use beauty as capital. Young women believe that their appearance is important because it can help them seize opportunities and allow them to cope with difficulties regarding gender discrimination in the workforce or unstable family relationships (Dippner, 2018). It is a widespread phenomenon that *Wanghong*, a Chinese term for internet celebrities or influencers who are famous for their looks, use their hyperfeminine appearance and makeup to attract audiences and generate wealth by advertising products. The ability to create money from hyperfeminine looks and makeup could encourage the imitation of

young girls who hope to create capital for themselves. This is exacerbated by the widespread availability of social media, such as *Douyin* (Chinese TikTok) and *Xiaohongshu* (Chinese social media platform).

Another vague motivation for applying makeup is identified as entertainment and creativity. Robertson (2021) found that new digital technology has made it possible for new makeup styles to develop. Makeup is categorized by many as a hobby that enhances and improves one's creativity (Robertson, 2021). Many women have remarked on their enjoyment in seeing the result of the makeup, the process of putting on makeup, and utilizing makeup for their creativity (Robertson, 2021).

Along with the rise of short video platforms such as *Douyin*, many people, including teenagers, have started to experiment with different styles of makeup and have even transformed makeup into a form of art or use makeup to transform themselves into fictional characters. In fact, it is popular in China for teenagers to “cosplay” anime characters by using makeup techniques that exaggerates one’s features to make them look more unreal, almost illustrated (Yang, 2022; Peirson-Smith, 2015). They often receive compliments from peers who also enjoy watching anime. However, the use of makeup for “cosplay” happens infrequently, and the reason why one would want to wear makeup daily is not addressed. This is especially true when makeup is generally not allowed in Chinese schools, as reported by all the interviewees who attend a local high school in China.

Some women have also claimed that they use makeup to create a new identity, to hide their true identity, or to practice individual power (Pourrajabi and Ghobadi, 2020). By using makeup to create their idealized identity, women conform to the belief that their appearance is associated with their personality, and makeup is used to present an attractive personality and to

appeal to societal values. When makeup is used, they also believe that they can do things that they were not able to do with their original appearance, such as feeling confident (Pourrajabi and Ghobadi, 2020). There are also instances when women use makeup to hide their physical and mental state to conceal their true identities. Robertson (2021) found that women utilize makeup to obscure their age to create a “socially desired” age, in which the young want to be perceived as mature and the old want to be perceived as younger. Makeup becomes a medium for women to achieve and create a new identity that fits societal expectations. However, many women, especially those of an older age, are dissatisfied with this expectation and find it conflicting with their true identity (Robertson, 2021).

The motivation to improve self-esteem and boost confidence by wearing makeup has been repeatedly found in previous studies. Young Chinese women have expressed their dissatisfaction with their appearance to explain their use of makeup to gain confidence (Sun, 2023). In South Korea, a neighboring country that has similar beauty standards to China, it is theorized that higher self-esteem discourages girls from using makeup (Kim and Yang, 2023). Therefore, Kim and Yang (2023) concluded that low self-esteem can lead to an increase in makeup use and that teenage girls with low self-esteem tend to use makeup as their method of appearance management. However, this method is not considered appropriate by older generations because of the opinion that makeup harms teenagers' growth. China faces a similar problem in which most elders are against the use of makeup among teenagers. A supportive and open-minded family would need to be present for one to feel more confident in makeup. It is also found that people who have social anxiety, negative self-perception, public self-consciousness, and mental health issues put on makeup to enhance their self-esteem and social confidence (Robertson, 2008).

An acceptable and common explanation for why teenage girls use makeup is peer pressure along with the pressure of social media. Social media, which captivates its audience with its aesthetics, imposes impractical and unattainable expectations of beauty on women (Bue, 2020; Sun, 2023). Sun's (2023) investigation into *Xiaohongshu* discovered that social media influencers play a huge role in constructing female beauty standards that are usually unrealistic. The influencers construct these beauty standards by associating their gender identity as a female with these standards and reinforcing these standards through their interactions with their audiences (Sun, 2023). As teenagers gain more access to social media platforms like *Xiaohongshu*, they can feel obligated to apply makeup to express their femininity and to follow society's standards of beauty to fit in. In South Korea, a country that shares a similar history regarding makeup policies in schools, wearing makeup has become a dominant part of teen culture, especially among girls (Han, 2020; Hwang & Cheon, 2011; Lee, 2020; Kim and Yang, 2023). Therefore, South Korean girls who wear makeup can have more mutual interests with other girls and are more likely to fit in with the peer culture. Although wearing makeup is not fully approved by South Korean society, especially those of older generations, girls continue to use makeup (Kim and Yang, 2023).

Another factor that encourages the use of makeup is social support from society and friends. Since the award festival for influencers was hosted by the popular Chinese social media platform Sina Weibo in 2016, *Wanghongs* have been favored among the young generation as "role models" due to their remarkably good-looking appearances (Dippner, 2018). Internet influencers can also promote makeup use by applying makeup in their social media posts. The influencer "DouDou Babe" posts makeup tutorials on *Xiaohongshu* and shows her flawless and structured face after using certain makeup techniques. The compliments she receives from the

audience reflect society's preference for women whose facial features align with that of beauty standards (Sun, 2023). During adolescence, social support from friends is critical for their development as a person, and that includes their habits regarding appearance management. For example, in South Korea, being socially supported by friends indicates that one will be included as a part of the teen culture, and one will most likely feel the need to put on makeup if they are encouraged to do so by their peers (Kim and Yang, 2023).

This paper explores the reasons behind the use of makeup by Chinese teenage girls in the 15 to 19-year-old age bracket. Although the current bodies of literature have assessed the reasons behind adult women's usage of makeup, many of those reasons, such as representing feminist ideologies and gaining erotic capital, do not necessarily account for why teenage girls use makeup due to the differences in social experiences. Furthermore, the research subjects of the current literature are predominantly from Western countries, which have different social and economic backgrounds compared to China and other Asian countries. To gain an understanding of the topic, 11 Chinese girls who are 15 to 19 years old, currently reside in China and use makeup at least once a week have been interviewed in the format of an online voice call. This method was chosen because it was the most efficient way to collect responses in a short amount of time and it can best address the research question with details from each individual interviewee.

Methodology

In order to obtain the most accurate and precise responses, a qualitative method of research, specifically interviews, has been chosen as the methodology of this research.

The data used for this research was selected based on the background of the interviewees. There were a few criteria that the interviewees had to meet: they had to be of Chinese origin (can

be mixed-race, for example, one interviewee is half Chinese and half Nepalis), identify as female, and be between the ages of 15 and 19. However, girls who do not currently reside in China will be excluded from the interview. This exclusion criteria were chosen because of the differences between the societal standards of China versus other countries. Teenagers are susceptible to being influenced by the society in which they reside. Therefore, Chinese teenagers who live outside of China may not provide a valid response to the research question, considering the distinct context.

The process by which the interviewees were found differed. Some of the interviewees were my friends while others were complete strangers. To find interviewees, a post was made on *Xiaohongshu*. This platform was chosen because it has an abundant amount of cosmetic content, which is most likely what the target interviewees will look at, and mostly female users (Ou, 2024). The post explained the purpose of this research paper and the format of the interview. After a user commented, a message was sent to them directly on the platform and invited them to do an interview when they were available. The interviews were carried out via recorded voice calls on the social media platform WeChat. The interviewees are anonymous, and the only personal information they were required to respond to was their age, the province in China that they live in, and the type of school (e.g., public, private, international) that they attend (if they do). All interviewees provided consent to reveal these personal details in the paper. The interviewees were asked a minimum of ten questions and several follow-up questions.

To analyze the responses, a table was created for the question “Why do you use makeup?” Due to the small number of responses, this method allowed finding themes between different responses efficiently and similarities between the interviewees who gave the same responses. On the left column of the table, the demographic information of the interviewee was

recorded. On the right column of the table, the individual responses were typed. If the interviewee responded in English, the response was directly typed. If the interviewee responded in Chinese, the response was translated from Chinese to English. For Chinese words and slang terms that do not directly translate into a specific English word, their meanings were interpreted based on the context and described in English. Translations were double-checked by a native Chinese speaker fluent in English. Some of the common themes that were found in these interviews include: to gain confidence, to cover skin problems, and to look good in pictures. To determine which themes each response corresponded to, they were separated into “external” and “internal” reasons and then categorized into more specific themes. For example, to cover up skin problems would be an “external” reason and to gain confidence would be an “internal” reason. However, this process can be paradoxical sometimes. For example, covering up skin problems using makeup can be a way that one gains confidence, but gaining confidence is categorized as an “internal” reason instead of “external.”

Results and Discussion

The responses of 11 teenage girls who use makeup and live in China were analyzed. A recurring answer in the responses of more than three interviewees is considered a theme. This research identifies six major themes: gaining confidence, concealing facial imperfections, being presentable in pictures, looking energetic, reducing stress and pressure, and easing the transition to becoming a woman. Although some of these themes were anticipated based on past studies and research, these themes provide a different understanding of the experience and the expectations of Chinese teenage girls and the culture of makeup in China.

Table to show the information of the eleven girls

Age	Province of residence	Type of School
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16	Guangdong	International High School
15	Guangdong	Local High School
16	Guangdong	International High School
16	Guangdong	International High School
17	Tianjin (Tianjin is not in any province but an independent city)	Local High School
17	Hunan	Local High School
17	Hunan	Arts High School
18	Jiangxi	Local High School
19	Zhejiang	University
18	Shanxi	University
19	Guangxi	Local High School & Preparatory Course

Gaining Confidence

As mentioned by more than half the interviewees, gaining confidence is one of the most important reasons why Chinese teenage girls wear makeup. Confidence, defined as “a feeling of having little doubt about yourself and your abilities,” is crucial and favorable in the development of teenagers (Cambridge Dictionary, 2024a). Previous research on South Korean girls has predicted that low self-esteem is closely linked with the girls’ tendency to use more makeup. Low self-esteem is when a person is extremely critical of themselves (Better Health Channel, 2014). In other words, low self-esteem means a lack of confidence. Consequently, it is also anticipated that girls who lack confidence will also be inclined to apply makeup. One interviewee mentioned, “*I pay lots of attention to my appearance, so after putting on makeup, I feel more confident about myself*” (17, Tianjin, Local High School).

A possible cause of a lack of confidence is the prevalence of social media. Prior research has shown that social media enforces unrealistic beauty expectations on women and that most young Chinese women feel unsatisfied with their appearances (Sun, 2023). Given that all interviewees were active users of Chinese social media platforms such as *Xiaohongshu* and *Douyin*, it is possible that all of the interviewees were influenced by the beauty standards on the internet to some extent. Apart from famous influencers, users who post “pretty” pictures or videos of themselves often receive compliments too. In order to be complimented, many girls make an effort to look the way that other girls have been praised for through the use of makeup. This is also where the term “*Wanghong Zhuang*” (internet celebrity makeup) comes from in Chinese.

When one is unable to be given compliments that others have been, one may feel a lack of self-confidence in their appearance, encouraging them to use makeup to alter their appearance into what they believe will be approved. For the girls who have already benefitted from the internet for their appearance, they continue to wear makeup to seek the compliments they have received in the past. As one interviewee said, “*I am a small influencer with 54k followers on Douyin, and I’m scared that people will recognize me when I’m outside without makeup on and they might say you look different from the videos that you post, it feels kinda weird*” (age 16, *Guangdong, International High School*). Makeup, in this situation, acts as a tool that proposes confidence. If a girl looks the same as she does in her videos, she is guaranteed to be complimented by her followers, boosting her confidence.

Confidence can also be used to improve performance. One interviewee who attends an arts school and plays the double bass claimed “*Putting on makeup doesn’t really affect my performance, but I think it affects my ability to perform. A suitable makeup can make my*

performance on stage more outstanding” (age 17, Hunan, Arts School). For this interviewee, she feels stressed about having to perform on stage and she wants to be able to show her ability to play the double bass well. To cope with stress and nervousness, she uses makeup and associates it with her ability to present skillfully. This creates a system in which when she applies makeup, it will increase her confidence level which also increases her capability of performing well.

Concealing Facial Imperfections

Chinese girls have also expressed that makeup can be used to cover skin problems and unwanted facial features, which has not been frequently addressed by previous literature.

Skin problems, such as acne, are more commonly seen on teenage girls’ faces due to their unstable levels of hormones when entering puberty. One interviewee mentioned, *“It [makeup] is used to cover up my acne and acne scars and other imperfections on my skin” (age 16, Guangdong, International High School).* Even though other methods for removing acne and acne scars exist, such as going to a beauty clinic, makeup takes less time and costs less, which could explain why makeup is preferred over other practices. Another interviewee also mentioned, *“I would be bothered by the acne all over my face... if I were to see someone” (age 17, Tianjin, Local High School).* In this situation, the interviewee from Tianjin seems to only care about her skin problems when she is viewing herself from the perspective of others, not for her own needs. Additionally, she also claimed that she only wears makeup when she leaves the house and goes to school, further demonstrating that she uses makeup due to her beliefs about the perception of others.

Using makeup to cover up “dark eye circles” is a skin problem that is mentioned by participants too. “Dark eye circles” is believed to be caused by staying up late, and there is no scientifically proven way to completely remove it. Therefore, makeup is the most effective

method to temporarily remove them. One interviewee claimed, *“I have naturally heavy dark eye circles...”* (age 15, Guangdong, Local High School). Like the interviewee from Tianjin, however, she also only wears makeup when she goes to school or hangs out with her friends. “Dark eye circles,” again, seem to be less of her own concern, but instead an internalization of others’ expectations. This demonstrates that covering her “dark eye circles” is a way of fulfilling others’ expectations.

A dark skin tone is another issue that some interviewees are trying to cover using makeup. Different from that of Western societies which believe that looking tanned is better than looking pale, Chinese society has had a long history of preferring whiter skin tones. At first, in ancient China, whiter skin tones meant that one was not involved in laborious works such as farming. In other words, one was of high status and did not have to toil in the fields for a living. Later, in modern China, whiter skin tones, a typical feature of the Europeans, were praised due to beliefs that Europeans are superior to the Chinese for their advanced technology and victories in wars. The legacy of this beauty standard has lasted until today, resulting in skincare products that claim to “brighten,” or in other words, “whiten” one’s skin, being exclusively sold in Asia (Yeung, 2015). Makeup products, especially foundations and concealers, lack shades of relatively darker skin tones that would fit the typical Asian skin.

Young teenage girls in this study are influenced by this long-lasting beauty standard too. One interviewee claimed, *“I have a darker skin tone and it's quite abrupt on my face, so I usually just cover it up with a whiter foundation”* (age 15, Guangdong, Local High School). Due to the fact that having a darker skin tone is quite common for Asians, calling it “abrupt” seems to be odd for someone who was born with this feature. Another interviewee mentioned, *“I would be bothered by...the uneven skin tone if I were to see someone”* (age 17, Tianjin, Local High

School). As mentioned above, she does not wear makeup for herself, but rather to live up to the expectations of the people around her, which includes Chinese society and its beauty standards for Chinese women.

One unwanted facial feature that was also frequently discussed in interviews is a flat nose. After the economic reform led by Deng in the late 20th century, beauty standards in China praised the facial features of those of Europeans, including a tall nose. However, to obtain a tall nose permanently would mean to undergo plastic surgery to lift the nose bone. Consequently, makeup became the most accessible way for one to create the illusion of a tall nose through contouring and highlighting. This technique is also used by the interviewee, as she mentioned, *“My nose is kind of flat, but if I apply contour, it can completely fix the problem”* (age 17, Tianjin, Local High School). Furthermore, she also claims that *“If it’s just a little time to fix this [flat nose] problem, then why not spend some time to do so?”* (age 17, Tianjin, Local High School). The flat nose insecurity is somewhat quick and easy to tackle by using makeup, and the returning benefit seems to be higher than the time and effort that is invested in fixing the issue, encouraging girls to do so often.

Being Presentable in Pictures

Rarely mentioned by current bodies of literature, another reason Chinese teenage girls use makeup is to look presentable in pictures. These pictures, if decided to be satisfactory by the girls, are usually posted on social media platforms. In China today, there are many criteria for a “good” picture, and “*Shangjing*” makeup is one of them. In Chinese, the term “*Shangjing*” (to look good in the camera) is created for this reason. “*Shangjing*” makeup is often exaggerated or bold makeup to cope with the fact that many believe that their makeup becomes less obvious when captured on camera. One interviewee mentioned, *“It also makes me happier because when*

you're taking photos outside, for example when you're hanging out with your friends and you guys want to take selfies and you want to post it on social media, putting on makeup makes me look pretty nice on social media" (age 17, Guangdong, International School). The interviewee feels content when she applies makeup to take photos that will be shared on social media, but not necessarily when she is alone. The interviewee also mentioned, *"Wearing makeup can make myself look prettier in others' perspectives" (age 17, Guangdong, International School).* From these responses, it can be inferred that the interviewee values others' opinions of her more than her own opinions of herself, and that makeup is not used to appreciate her appearance, but rather to receive external validation of her beauty.

Similarly, another interviewee mentioned, *"The reason I wear makeup on vacation and when I travel is mainly because I can look better in pictures" (16, Guangdong, International School).* Given that this interviewee is a small influencer and that her followers "often request for pictures", using makeup allows her to maintain her appearance as seen in her videos to keep her current followers satisfied and to attract new followers. Putting on makeup and taking photos has become a social activity that demonstrates that one is living a desirable and fun life and having a beautiful appearance. By creating an illusion of an "ideal" life through these photos, it feeds on the self-esteem of girls and establishes their high status on the internet.

Looking Energetic

Although previous studies have found that makeup enables one to look attractive, looking energetic is more of a concern for Chinese teenage girls. Looking energetic is often achieved by using makeup to cover flaws on the face. Many girls believe that the facial feature of dark eye circles is what makes them look unenergetic. Given that dark eye circles can be caused by genetics and allergies, most people associate it with a lack of sleep and rest, therefore, being the

barrier to achieving an “energetic looking” face. One interviewee stated, “*I use concealer...to look energetic... otherwise my dark eye circles would be hanging around all day.*” (age 16, Guangdong, International School). In this situation, the function of makeup is to cover up a facial imperfection that society considers unhealthy and to therefore create the perception that one is living a healthy and easy life where one does not have to stay up late to do work. This is reflected in one interviewee’s response in which she claimed, “*It [makeup] can make me look energetic because you know, I’m a high schooler...Studying makes me look tired*” (age 17, Hunan, Local High School).

Apart from dark eye circles, another facial feature that girls claim makes them look unenergetic is dull skin. Similar to that of dark eye circles, dull skin is usually associated with health problems. One interviewee mentioned, “*I have dull skin when I don’t sleep enough but when I use makeup, I look more energetic*” (age 18, Jiangxi, Local High School). Again, makeup is used to conceal a believed imperfection in order to look healthier.

Reducing Stress and Pressure

In previous bodies of literature, pressure from social media is often identified as a reason why women use makeup. *Xiaohongshu* is known to promote unrealistic beauty standards through influencers (Sun, 2023). However, in this research, it is also found that not only are influencers aggravating the standards, but they are also compelled to follow that standard on the internet and in real life in order to please the audience. One interviewee claimed, “*I wish to appear in real life exactly like what I look like on Douyin*” (age 16, Guangdong, International School). For her, wearing makeup helps her cope with stress from the internet in that it guarantees her followers that her online persona her true persona and not a fake identity.

In a 2008 survey conducted by China Youth and Children Research Center (CYCRC), approximately 78.3% of high school students responded that they spend at least 8 hours at school every day. Chinese high schools place their students under relentless pressure until they graduate and move on into college (China.org.cn). Although not all interviewees attend a local high school, most of them have this experience, which they find stressful and demanding. For example, one interviewee said, *“If you include the time of being in school, then it’s usually around 10 hours”* (15, Guangdong, Local High School). She also mentioned, *“The stress level is above average, and [the stress] comes from my teachers and family...they want me to go to a good university”* (age 15, Guangdong, Local High School). In another interview, the interviewee recalled her senior year schedule in high school: *“I wake up at 5 every day to get to class at 5:30, I study from then until 1 am in the morning...the stress level in high school is always very high”* (age 18, Shanxi, University Freshman). As a result, constant pressure from high school, or specifically, the high expectations of teachers and families, is one cause of low self-esteem among Chinese teenagers. As one interviewee mentioned, *“Trying to cope with this burden, many [Chinese teenage girls] have found makeup as a way of relieving stress”* (19, Guangxi, Local High School and Preparatory Course). However, using makeup as a source of alleviating pressure is unsustainable: when makeup is removed, confidence is also taken away. In this situation, a vicious cycle is created in which the girls are dependent on makeup to feel confident. This is also an explanation for the girls’ persistence in applying makeup before leaving the house. As one interviewee expressed: *“Makeup before I leave the house? That is certain”* (age 19, Zhejiang, University Freshman).

For Chinese teenage girls, pressure and stress also exist in other forms. Similar to social media, another source of stress comes from not fitting into beauty standards. One interviewee

mentioned, *“It [makeup] can reduce my appearance anxiety and make myself like myself more”* (19, Zhejiang, University Freshman). In this situation, makeup is something that helps one to alter their facial features and therefore reduces one’s stress about not being able to fit in with the standards of beauty.

Easing the Transition to Becoming an Adult Woman

Less discussed by previous studies due to the differences in the age group, makeup is used by Chinese teenage girls to appear and feel more like an adult woman. A belief held by the interviewees and the Chinese society is that a sign of becoming a woman is when a girl starts to pay attention to their appearance. One interviewee mentioned, *“Every girl wants themselves to look pretty, and this is a reason why I wear makeup”* (age 16, Guangdong, International School). Despite the fact that not all girls might have an interest in pursuing an aesthetic appearance, nevertheless, the interviewee emphasizes “every girl” in this response, showing the interviewee’s internalization of the view that the female identity is closely linked with beauty and appearance. Similarly, another interviewee mentioned, *“At this age, it is normal that you would want to become pretty and you are conscious that you want to show that you are physically in good condition [in terms of the face]”* (age 17, Hunan, Arts School). In this response, the interviewee uses the term “at this age” and by doing so, she refers to her own age. Although she is still considered a teenager, her age is close to that as of a “young woman.” Again, she also associates the female identity with appearance. Because they are so closely linked, as demonstrated by the two interviewees, makeup can be perceived as something that can help girls prove that they are pursuing being beautiful, therefore making them eligible to be considered as young women.

Conclusion

While previous bodies of literature were able to identify certain reasons that overlap with the findings of this research, Chinese teenage girls had different reasons from women of a relatively older age. By examining the responses of eleven Chinese teenage girls, this research finds six common reasons and motivations for the use of makeup: gaining confidence, concealing facial imperfections, being presentable in pictures, looking energetic, reducing stress and pressure, and easing the transition to becoming an adult woman. Even though all the interviewees come from different backgrounds, similarities were discovered between each of their responses. Therefore, it can be concluded that their reasoning for applying and using makeup is all somewhat affected by the beauty standards of Chinese society, stress from school, and the pursuit of validation. The significance of this paper is in that it demonstrates that society's beauty standards can have far-reaching effects and that makeup is more of a social activity for Chinese teenage girls.

Nonetheless, this paper has a limited sample of interviewees in that they are all Han Chinese, which may not accurately reflect all possible motives and occasions in which makeup is applied by Chinese teenage girls of other ethnic groups, given that there are 56 identified groups in China. Future research could potentially investigate girls of ethnic groups other than Han and identify more explanations for the use of makeup by the girls and other factors that influence their reasoning to have a more comprehensive understanding of beauty in China. Future studies could also explore reasons why Chinese teenage girls do not use makeup and compare the difference in reasoning with this research.

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